

Electrochemical Reduction of the Complexes of Cadmium(II) with *N*-(2-Ethoxy)phenylmalonamic Acid and *N*-(2-Chloro)phenylmalonamic Acid

AJAY TANEJA, P. N. HARI SHARMA, D. S. SETH and ASHOK KUMAR*

Chemical Laboratories, St. John's College, Agra-282 002

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The use of polarographic data for the study of complexation is well known^{1,2}. There are reports³ on polarographic study of metals with malonic acid and its derivatives. A survey of literature reveals that polarographic study on reactive methylene compounds of malonamic series is still lacking which have been found to be excellent starting materials for the synthesis of various types of chemotherapeutic agents and analytical reagents both for organic and inorganic qualitative and quantitative analyses by some workers⁴ of this laboratory and hence it was thought worthwhile to undertake the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} produces a single well-defined reversible reduction wave in each case. The linear plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ for Cd^{II} and its complexes indicated the diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction. The plots of $[\log i/(i_d - i)]$ vs $E_{d.o.}$ for each polarogram were found to be linear with a slope of 31 ± 2 mV, indicating the reversibility of the electrode process involving two electrons.

The half-wave potential of Cd^{II} shifted towards more cathodic value and the diffusion current decre-

ased with increasing concentration of the ligand in each case. This indicated the complex formation. The plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $\log C_x$ were found to be straight lines showing the formation of single complex species, which were in equilibrium with each other. Reported method² was applied to determine the composition and stability constant of the complex. The polarographic characteristics for both the systems have been incorporated in Table 1.

A perusal of the Table 1 indicates that Cd^{II} forms a single complex with EPMA as well as with CPMA. The value of coordination number (J) comes out to be 2 in both the cases. The composition of the complexes formed were $[\text{Cd}(\text{EPMA})_2]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{CPMA})_2]$ with their stability constants $\log \beta_2 = 6.491$ and $\log \beta_2 = 6.897$ respectively.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Metal solution (0.1 M) and potassium chloride solution were prepared in double-distilled water and was standardised gravimetrically. Sodium salts of *N*-(2-ethoxy)phenylmalonamic acid and *N*-(2-chloro)phenylmalonamic acid were the sources of

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TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Cd^{II}-N-(2-ETHOXY)PHENYLMALONAMIC ACID (EPMA) AND N-(2-CHLORO)PHENYLMALONAMIC ACID (CPMA) SYSTEMS

[Cd^{II}]=1×10⁻³ M, μ =2.0 (KCl), pH=6.0, Temp =25±0.1°, $m=2.38$ mg/s⁻¹, $t=3.4$ s, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.1$ mg^{2/3}s^{-1/6} (in 2.0 M KCl, open-circuit): $k_{corr}=62.5$ cm

Concn. M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV
[EPMA]⁻			
0.0000	5.98	0.600	30
0.0005	5.80	0.610	31
0.001	5.50	0.625	32
0.002	5.20	0.642	31
0.004	5.01	0.660	30
0.008	4.92	0.680	33
[CPMA]⁻			
0.0000	7.61	0.600	30
0.0005	7.41	0.610	30
0.001	6.93	0.630	31
0.005	6.73	0.660	32
0.01	6.50	0.680	33
0.05	6.31	0.700	33

EPMA and CPMA respectively ; their stock solutions (0.1 M) were prepared in double-distilled water.

Polarograms of Cd^{II} alone and Cd^{II} with varying concentration of each of the ligands in potassium chloride as supporting electrolyte at pH 6.0±0.10 were recorded on a Toshniwal CLO2A polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal Polyflex PL 50 galvanometer. The capillary had $m=2.38$ mg s⁻¹, $t=3.5$ s in 2.0 M potassium chloride at 62.5 cm

effective height of the mercury column. Pure nitrogen gas was bubbled through the test solutions before recording the polarograms. The ionic strength ($\mu=2.0$) was kept constant by potassium chloride and pH of the test solutions was fixed at 6.0±0.1 by dilute acetic acid/sodium hydroxide solutions. All the observations were made at 25±1°.

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